

Law, AI and robotics: Spain

[WP4 – Artificial Intelligence and robotics]

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Executive summary

This report which focuses on legal developments and analyses the law related to AI and robotics in Spain is divided in six sections.

The introduction briefly summarises the Spanish law system, the objective of the report, the methodological approach and the state of the art of legislative work in the Parliament. After this it outlines the scope and limitations.

The report explores five questions on legal developments in Spain related to AI and robotics, i.e., recent developments, plans to implement new legislation, creation of new regulatory bodies, case law and other future relevant developments. The research did not identify any significant developments, however we anticipate there will be developments in terms of finding solutions to issues generated by AI and robotics in the near future.

The next part focusses on specific legal issues. It explores how Spanish law regulates/addresses algorithmic bias and discrimination. It also looks at how the law addresses intellectual property issues related to works created by AI. With regard to both these, in Spain there is no special regulation; the general system, Fundamental Rights and Intellectual Property Act, can provide solutions. It is necessary to go to these general norms to find solutions. In relation to discrimination, there is specific act on gender discrimination and minorities (LGTB community or disabled people). The report also highlights one other relevant issue - criminal liability for robots' acts.

The discussion in Spain about the legal aspects in robotics and AI can be divided in two parts: how the robots and AI will be impact on the legal praxis and how we can find solutions for the new legal problems the Spanish society is going to face with this technological revolution.

Spain is not at the top of the discussion at the international level, and there are several legal gaps, but in our opinion, in the next years will be important change about the topics, particularly if changes come from EU institutions. The legal system in Spain will try to find solutions for the legal challenges of the AI from general solutions. Though there is very less specific legislation on AI, general solutions could be adapted to this new technology in particular with the interpretation of general rules by the jurisprudence, with special focus on the Constitutional Court. The main gap for this solution is the lack of knowledge of judges about how AI works; however, with the proper training this could be resolved. Intellectual property, civil responsibility, criminal responsibility and contract law, with the proper interpretation, could provide solutions for the problems that, AI nowadays presents.

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List of acronyms/abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
AI	Artificial intelligence
CCS	Constitutional Court Sentence
D	Deliverable
FR	Fundamental right
GDPR	General data protection regulation
IPA	Intellectual Property Act

Table 1: List of acronyms/abbreviations

Glossary of terms

Term	Explanation
Artificial intelligence	The science and engineering of machines with capabilities that are considered intelligent (i.e., intelligent by the standard of <i>human</i> intelligence). Major applications of AI technology are in transportation, education, finance, industry, healthcare, marketing, management, telecommunications, entertainment and defence, amongst other fields. Important subfields of AI were found to include: knowledge representation and automated reasoning, artificial neural networks, machine learning, computer vision, computer audition, natural language processing, expert systems, data mining, intelligent agent systems and automated planning, evolutionary computation. [SIENNA D4.1]
Robotics	The field of science and engineering that deals with the design, construction, operation, and application of robots. Major applications of robots are in transportation, industry, healthcare, education, entertainment, space exploration, defence, retail, companionship, housekeeping and other areas. Important subfields of robotics were found to include: robot mechanics, robot sensing, robot control (including many subareas, such as robot learning, adaptive control, developmental robotics, evolutionary robotics, cognitive robotics, behaviour-based robotics, robotic mapping and planning), robot locomotion, bio-inspired and soft robotics, humanoid robotics, microrobotics, nanorobotics, beam robotics, cloud robotics, swarm robotics, telerobotics, social robotics and human-robot interaction. [SIENNA D4.1]
Automated decision-making	Decision based solely on automated processing, including profiling, which produces legal effects concerning a data subject or similarly significantly affects him or her (GDPR, Article 22 (1)). It refers to individual decision-making made by automated means without any human involvement.
Machine learning	A set of approaches within AI where statistical techniques and data are used to “teach” computer systems how to perform particular tasks,

	without these systems being explicitly programmed to do so. (SIENNA D4.1, p. 11.)
Processing	any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction. Art 4(2) GDPR.
Organic Law	Any law or act that affect to fundamental rights. Needs 50% +1 of the votes of all MPs
Law	Any law. Need simple majority at the Parliament
Royal Law-Decree	A norm that has the same status as a law, made by the Government with the permission of the Parliament. Only in cases of extreme and urgency necessity
Royal Legislative Decree	A norm that has the same status as a law, made by the Government with the permission of the Parliament. The Parliament put the basics boundaries of the legislative Government's powers.

Table 2: Glossary of terms

1. Introduction

Spain is a constitutional Estate with 17 autonomous communities (Galicia, Asturias, Cantabria, País Vasco, Navarra, Aragón, Cataluña, Castilla León, La Rioja, Madrid, Castilla la Mancha, País Valenciano, Baleares, Murcia, Extremadura, Andalucía y Canarias) and two autonomous cities (Ceuta y Melilla). The Constitution gives separate powers to the State and to the autonomous communities but in a few areas they share these powers as could be all topics related to medicine, environmental or taxes. The Constitution does not make provisions to regulate AI and robotics; they would be subject to field-specific applicable laws and regulations e.g., use of robotics in medicine.

In Spain, there are four kinds of Acts, Ley Orgánica, Ley, Real Decreto Ley and Real Decreto Legislativo, that come from the Parliament. There are also norms that come from the Government (regulations) with different titles, e.g., Real Decreto, Orden ministerial or Orden de Comisión.

The **objective** of this report is to review the state of the law and current legal responses to developments in AI and robotics and determine how specific legal questions/issues are addressed in Spain.

The **methodology** used was a web scan (Google, Dialnet plus, Congreso de los Diputados and BOE¹) to identify laws, in the last ten years, that regulate robots and AI in general in Spain, and the result was that we found no one specific law. We used, in Spanish, terms as “inteligencia artificial”, “regulación en inteligencia artificial”, “normativa en inteligencia artificial” “robótica”, “regulación en robótica”, “normativa en robótica”) In the Google search, we added the term “España” to avoid results linked to South American countries.

There are three Non-legislative Motions (Proposición no de ley)² by the Government relevant to our research. The first one, by Popular Party, from 28th of June 2018 (about the use of AI in business and citizen’s rights)³ and the second one, by Ciudadanos Party, to create an international and European cooperation in AI, from 27th of July 2018.⁴ The third one, also by the Ciudadanos Party, focuses on the use of Big data analysis and AI to fight the high rate of unemployment.⁵

¹ Dialnet plus is a Law and social sciences web portal for journals and books <https://dialnet.unirioja.es/>. BOE is the Official newspaper where all laws from Spain are published www.boe.es The official site of the Parliament (Congreso de los Diputados) gives information about the state of all legislative work in progress www.congreso.es

² This is a resource that the opposition parties can use at the Parliament to incite the Government to start a new regulation.

³ Spain, Proposición no de ley sobre la protección de derechos ante la inteligencia artificial (Non-legislative Motion about the protection of rights with the use of artificial intelligent), 16 July 2018. http://www.congreso.es/public_oficiales/L12/CONG/BOCG/D/BOCG-12-D-391.PDF#page=20

⁴ Spain, Proposición no de ley sobre el impulso a la inversión y la cooperación europea e internacional en materia de inteligencia artificial (Non-legislative Motion about the impetus in investment and European cooperation in artificial intelligent), 12 September 2018. http://www.congreso.es/public_oficiales/L12/CONG/BOCG/D/BOCG-12-D-409.PDF#page=99

⁵ Spain, Proposición no de ley sobre el uso de macrodatos (Big Data) e inteligencia artificial en el ámbito laboral (Non-legislative Motion about the use of macrodata (Big Data) and artificial intelligent in workplace), 2 October 2018. http://www.congreso.es/public_oficiales/L12/CONG/BOCG/D/BOCG-12-D-423.PDF#page=27

We also asked select Spanish experts in the field of AI (from medicine, computer sciences, Big data analytics, law enforcement, etc.) and legal scholars for information and they gave us only one reference, i.e., the Real Decreto 1591/2009 that regulates the sanitary products, including the use of robots in sanitary service.⁶

2. Scope and limitations of the report

The robotics and AI legal debate in Spain is something new. It is really complicated to find any information about these topics because the lack of information and legislative motions in the Parliament. The Government crisis in the last five years doesn't make the best situation, with no a big majority, to face this challenge.

One particular challenge with the online research was separating Spanish websites and documents from Latin-American ones. Google does not do this kind of classification so it is not a big problem, but consumes time.

The scope of this report is as demarcated by task 4.2. of the SIENNA project.

3. Legal developments

- i. **Have developments in AI (i.e., automated decision-making systems, algorithmic systems, machine learning) and robotics led to amendments in constitutional or human rights and/or legislation bearing on constitutional or human rights?**

The answer to this question is no. There are critical issues related to constitutional rights (in Spain called fundamental rights) (FR). In Spain, there are several FRs that can be connected to AI and robotics. Art. 10.1 of the Constitution includes the right to personal dignity and free human development, understood as personal freedom to be what a person would want to be. Some AI in social networks have censured some photos of particular persons not allowing these persons to express themselves without injuring other people. There is no constitutional Court sentence but it is something that is in the general public debate.

Art.14 of the Spanish Constitution regulates the right to equality and prohibits discrimination based on birth, race, sex, religion, opinion. The Article is flexible enough to bring within its ambit future ways of discrimination (including those carried out using AI) linked to any other personal or social condition or circumstance.

⁶ Spain, Real Decreto por el que se regulan los productos sanitarios 1591/2009 (Royal Decree on the Regulation of Sanitary Products), 16 October 2009. <https://www.boe.es/boe/dias/2009/11/06/pdfs/BOE-A-2009-17606.pdf>

Particular cases have been adjudicated by the Courts in Spain related to moral integrity linked to AI in social network and internet browsers.⁷ E.g., the case of Olvido Hormigos, a woman sent an erotic video to her lover and he sent it to his friends via a social network and it ended in websites where it was available to anyone to find thanks to search algorithms.

The European Justice Court case law from 2014 about the right to be forgotten against Google, started in the Spanish Court.⁸ In this case, the arguments were linked to the right to privacy regulated by article 18 of the Spanish constitution. Google's algorithm linked Mr. Costeja González's name to two web pages of a very popular paper in Catalunya, La Vanguardia, which stated that Mr. Costeja González was confiscated and he was not able to get credit in any bank because every time they looked for him up, the top research result came up with that status although he his financial position had changed.⁹

In 2018, there was another decision of the Constitutional Court, case 58/2018¹⁰, of 4th June 2018, about article 18 (1) related to honour, personal and family privacy and self-image. In this case, two people, D.F.C. y M.F.C. fought against the newspaper El País. In its online newspaper library, there were several news from the 80s where these persons were sentenced for drug trafficking. They argued that it was a long time ago and demanded their rights to be forgotten. In this case the Court took paragraph 4 of article 18 to limit the use of computer and data processing to protect this right. The Court decided that the use of data by search AI should be limited and this particular information from long time ago should be not processed by algorithm but it could be accessed in the standard way (going to the newspaper library and finding it by hand).

- ii. **Have there been/are there attempts or plans to create or adopt new legislation in response to developments in AI and robotics (e.g., granting legal personhood to robots, prescribing civil or criminal liability for harms caused), or to regulate¹¹ how AI and robotics applications are designed, set up, commissioned or used? (e.g., regulation of algorithmic development or restrictions on the use of robots in certain conditions or sectors)**

In June 2018, the Ciudadanos Party and Popular Party signed two draft, Non-legislative Motions, to try to regulate AI, and the funding of innovation on AI and European and international cooperation. The drafts contain only a very basic information about the topics that the Government should regulate on several bills.

In September 2018, Ciudadanos Party signed another Non-legislative Motion, about the use of Big data analysis and AI to fight against unemployment. The idea is to use this technology to make it easier to connect the unemployed and companies. Another goal is to fight against workers' contract fraud; the

⁷ Diario El País, 26 April 2013. https://elpais.com/sociedad/2013/04/26/actualidad/1367001448_404152.html

⁸ Court of Justice of the European Union, Case C-131/12, *Google Spain SL, Google Inc v Agencia Española de Protección de Datos (AEDP) vs Mario Costeja González*, 13 May 2014.

⁹ García Garnica, María del Carmen, "La protección de los datos personales frente a su tratamiento <<on line>> por motores de búsqueda: el derecho al olvido digital" in Javier Valls Prieto (ed.), *Retos jurídicos por la sociedad digital*, Navarra, Thomson Reuters Aranzadi, 2018, pp. 107-136.

¹⁰ Constitutional Court, Case 58/ 2018, 7 July 2018 https://www.boe.es/diario_boe/txt.php?id=BOE-A-2018-9534

¹¹ This could be to restrict or advance the development or use of such applications.

new economy contract makes contracts shorter to avoid paying workers' benefits and hire them as self-employed or freelancers.

iii. Are there new regulatory bodies being set up to regulate AI and robotics? What are the developments on this front? (e.g., AI watchdogs, AI commission, Robotics commission)

Not at the moment. As of writing, there is no firm indication so far from the Spanish Government about creating a commission other any other bodies to regulate AI or robotics. However, there was in May 2018 a discussion group which created a white book, organised by the Economy and Business Office (Ministerio de Economía y Empresa).

The White Book focuses on economic impact of robotics in Spanish economy. It begins with a state of the art of robotics and future trends. It follows with a study of the socio-economic impact of robotics and how the R+D+I is at the international level and Spain. The next point of interest is how robotics R+D+I will be funded. Communication to society, how University degrees and master in robotics and trends should be are also included in its analysis. The white book ends with a strategy analysis for Spain in the next three years. There is no mention of ethical or legal issues related to robotics.

iv. Identify any significant case law or judgments¹² addressing human rights challenges¹³ of AI and robotics (if there are no judgments, you can refer to legal doctrine)

The research to find significant case law was carried out using WestLaw (Thomson Reuters). We looked for judgments from the Supreme Court in all areas (civil, criminal, administrative, labour and military) in the last five years and found there are no cases related to the goals of SIENNA project. The keywords used in the search were: "robot" "robótica" and "inteligencia artificial".

We also looked for case law in the search engine of the Constitutional Court with the same terms with no interesting result for SIENNA.

In Spain, the legal doctrine about AI and robotics is focussed on how AI will be introduced in legal practice (i.e., AI in court, AI in Law firm, etc.), how AI affect to a particular problem (AI in Real Estate market, labour market¹⁴, security, responsibility for damages¹⁵, Mediation and AI¹⁶) and the legal regulation of robots.¹⁷

With regard to Human rights and AI and robots there are two important references. The general protection of constitutional rights and the impact in the concept of Estate is discussed in the work from

¹² Limited only to decisions in the highest courts – unless going further in depth is warranted.

¹³ For example, discrimination, inequality, privacy infringements, unfavourable work conditions, harm to life, bodily integrity, human safety and welfare, liability etc.

¹⁴ Puente Pérez, Esther, "Los robots en el Derecho del trabajo" in Moisés Barrio Andrés (ed.) *Derecho de los robots*, Wolters Kluwer, Madrid, 2018, pp. 151-168.

¹⁵ Diaz Alabart, S., *Robots y responsabilidad civil*, Reus, Madrid, 2018.

¹⁶ Bueno de la Mata, F., "Mediación electrónica e inteligencia artificial", *Actualidad civil*, nº1, 2015.

¹⁷ Barrio Andrés, M. et al., *Derecho de los robots*, Wolters Kluwer, Madrid, 2018.

Sánchez Barrilao.¹⁸ The second is about the protection of privacy right in the use of Big Data and artificial intelligence. This work studies the new challenges for privacy and how privacy should be protected in the new era and suggests developing new privacy crimes related to the misuse of AI and data analytics, for business¹⁹, security and police investigations²⁰.

v. Highlight any other relevant, potential future legal developments relating to AI and robotics identified in authoritative legal sources in your country

The search found no legal regulation, specific to AI and robotics. There are some Non-legislative motions in connection to the use of AI in some particular topics, as labour market or medicine, but not fully addressing 'AI' or 'robotics'.

On 5th December 2018, the new Spanish act on data protection and digital rights was published.²¹ The Act implements the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in the Spanish legal system. This proposal has different citizen's rights that can affect AI in several areas. For example, it covers net neutrality, right to oblige non-discrimination in the use of Internet by gender, social status, technological matters, elderly or rural (articles 80 and 81), use of AI to redirect internet flow should be aware of these conditions.

In the work place there are new rights e.g., privacy and use of digital devices in work place (article 87), disconnection outside the work place (article 88), privacy and video surveillance and sound recordings at the work place (article 89), geo-localization at work place (article 90) and new regulation of right to be forgotten on internet and social networks (articles 92 and 93). Finally, there is a provision about digital legacy, i.e., who can administrate the data of a death person (article 96).

In the Spanish Data Protection Act, there is also the possibility for political parties to profile person's political data for sending information during electoral campaign (3rd Final disposition). This kind of activity will be done by robots although there is no explicit mention.

The provisions related to workers and public servants (articles 87-90) can have an impact of the use of data and particular devices used to control the workers. This would mean some AI and robots can have a limited actions and the use of related data would be restricted.

¹⁸ Sánchez Barrilao, José F., "Derecho Constitucional, desarrollo informático e inteligencia artificial: aproximación a la propuesta del Parlamento Europeo a favor de una regulación sobre robótica" in Javier Valls Prieto (ed), *Retos jurídicos por la sociedad digital*, Navarra, Thomson Reuters Aranzadi, 2018, pp. 21-76.

¹⁹ Valls Prieto, J., "Nuevas formas de protección penal de la intimidad", *CPC*, 120, 2016, pp. 175-214.

²⁰ Valls Prieto, J., *Problemas jurídico penales asociados a las nuevas técnicas de prevención y persecución del crimen mediante inteligencia artificial*, Dykinson, Madrid, 2017.

²¹ Spain, Ley Orgánica 3/2018 de Protección de Datos Personales y garantía de los derechos digitales (Organic Act of Personal Data Protection and Guarantee of the Digital Rights), 5 December 2018, <https://www.boe.es/boe/dias/2018/12/06/pdfs/BOE-A-2018-16673.pdf>

4. Analysis of specific legal issues

This section explores selected specific legal issues related to AI and robotics. We explore/elaborate, for AI, two critical issues:

- Algorithmic bias and discrimination (including automated decision-making systems), i.e., how does the law deal with issues of algorithmic bias and discrimination?
- Intellectual property issues related to works created by AI, i.e., does the law ascribe intellectual property rights (e.g., copyright, patent right, design rights, trademarks, etc.) for AI generated works or inventions? Who owns such intellectual property rights?

For robotics, we will explore:

- Creation of a specific legal status for robots, i.e., legal personhood or electronic personality, i.e., has the law created/does the law recognise a specific legal status for robots? Are there any movements in this direction?
- Safety and civil liability issues: who is liable for damage caused by robots?

4.1. Artificial intelligence

4.1.1. Algorithmic bias and discrimination (including automated decision-making systems)

In the Spanish legal system, there are several areas where algorithmic bias and discrimination could be covered. The general regulation of discrimination could be found in some FRs in the Constitution and their protection in some paragraphs of the penal code. Apart of that there is a national Organic Law from 2007²² about effective equality between men and women, that is not only for the economic sector, but for all life areas, as could be administrative procedurals, cultural and social life, etc. There are also the Autonomous Communities Acts, e.g., one from Castilla Leon disabled people discrimination, from 2014;²³ Balears Islands' equality between women and men Act, from 2016²⁴ or the Canary Islands for non-discrimination for no gender discrimination and recognition of transgender

²² Spain, Ley Orgánica 3/2007 para la igualdad efectiva de mujeres y hombres (Organic Act for the effective equality of women and men), 22 March 2007. <https://www.boe.es/buscar/pdf/2007/BOE-A-2007-6115-consolidado.pdf>

²³ Spain (Castille Lion) , Ley 2/2013 de igualdad de oportunidades para personas con discapacidad (Act for the equal opportunities for disable persons), 15 May 2013. <https://www.boe.es/boe/dias/2013/06/06/pdfs/BOE-A-2013-5998.pdf>

²⁴ Spain (Balears Islands), Ley 11/2016 de igualdad de mujeres y hombres (Act of women and men equality), 28 July 2016. <https://www.boe.es/buscar/pdf/2016/BOE-A-2016-7994-consolidado.pdf>

rights Act, from 2014.²⁵ Cataluña has an equality between women and men Act, effective from 2015²⁶; and an Act to protect lesbian, gays, transgender and intergender rights and to eradicate homophobic, biphobic and transphobic discrimination, from 2014.²⁷ Andalusian has similar regulation on gender equality from 2007²⁸ and renewed in 2018.²⁹

In all this legislation there is no mentions of ‘algorithms’ ,‘algorithmic bias’ or ‘AI discrimination’. Despite that, these principles could still be interpreted as prohibiting algorithmic bias or AI discrimination..

The Spanish Constitution could be used as a frame where all the other acts are included. In Spain there are several FRs that can be affected by AI. These include:

- **The right to personal dignity, inviolability of rights and free human development.** Regulated by Art. 10.1 of the Constitution, this article calls for respect of the personal dignity, with right to a personal dignity and free human development understood as the personal freedom to be what a person wants to be.
Some AI in social networks have censored some photos of particular persons not allowing these person to express themselves without injuring other people. There is no constitutional Court case or judgment, but it is something that is in the public debate (society and legal).
- **Right to equality and ban of discrimination.**
Art. 14 regulates the right to equality and prohibits discrimination based on birth, race, sex, religion and opinion. It regulates also future ways of discrimination linked to any other personal or social condition or circumstance.
This article is interpreted as the equality to the law, in particular against administration and State discrimination, but I can be considered as well for any other discriminations.³⁰ This right

²⁵ Spain (Canary Islands), Ley 8/2014 de no discriminación por motivos de identidad de género y de reconocimiento de los derechos de las personas transexuales (Non-discrimination for gender identity and transgender people’s rights recognition Act) 28 October 2014. <https://www.boe.es/buscar/pdf/2014/BOE-A-2014-11995-consolidado.pdf>

²⁶ Spain (Catalunya), Llei 17/2015 d’igualtat efectiva de dones i homes (Women and men effective equality Act), 21 July 2015. <http://portaldogc.gencat.cat/utillsEADOP/PDF/6919/1436051.pdf>

²⁷ Spain (Catalunya), Ley 11/2014 para garantizar los derechos de lesbianas, gays, bisexuales, transgéneros e intersexuales y para erradicar la homofobia, la bifobia y la transfobia (Lesbians, gays, bisexual, transgender and interseual’s rights guaranties and to eradicate homophobic, bifobic and transfobic), 10 October 2014. <https://www.boe.es/boe/dias/2014/11/20/pdfs/BOE-A-2014-11990.pdf>

²⁸ Spain (Andalusia), Ley para la promoción de la igualdad de género (Promotion of gender equality Act), 26 November 2017. <https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/export/drupaljda/Ley-12-2007.pdf>

²⁹ Spain (Andalusia), Ley 7/2018 por la que se modifica la Ley 13/2017, de 26 de noviembre, de medidas de prevención y protección integral contra la violencia de género (Act for the modification of Act 13/2017, from 26 November, about the comprehensive protection agaisnst gender violence), 30 July 2018. <https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/boja/2018/148/1>

³⁰ Ballaguer Callejón, María L., “Principio de igualdad y Derechos individuales”, F. Ballaguer Callejón, et al. (eds.), *Manual de Derecho Constitucional*, Tecnos, Madrid, 2018, pp. 91-174.

has been interpreted also as the right to difference in a way that advances the goal of no discrimination³¹.

That means any AI or algorithm that bases its decision making by these kind of variables (birth, race, sex, religion and opinion) would not be allowed under the Constitutional system in Spain. All persons have to be treated as equally as possible- in particular those who have one of the expressed characteristics listed in article 14.

One might be allowed to make a positive discrimination from AI and an algorithm if its decision tries to solve a discrimination issue, which already exists in a society, in relation to a minority (women, black people, gypsies, homosexual, etc.)

The use of algorithms in medicine (to know if some patients could have a particular treatment) or by police (to know who could be a dangerous person or the no go areas) or by the private sector to know if somebody can get an insurance or a credit, would be not allowed if it restricts the self-esteem or there is any condition that discriminates a person for different reasons as the goal of the distinction. If an algorithm, used in medicine, says somebody cannot get a particular treatment for being a woman, gay or poor, that will not be acceptable.

- **Privacy right.**

The GDPR, directly applicable in Spain, also regulates algorithmic bias and discrimination – relevant articles include Article 22 (which regulates automated individual decision-making and profiling).

Further, art. 18 of the Spanish constitution protects privacy rights. Clause 4 of this article limits computer use of personal data that is understood as risk itself for privacy.³² The citizen has the right to control the information that is in a computer system,³³ understood as *habeas data*. So this right has two sides: one, as a protection of privacy and another, as a control of the data that the AI and robots can have, and use in their systems.

From 5th December 2018, there is a new Data Protection Act³⁴ that follows the basic grounds of the GDPR. There is regulated what are the minimum standard in security measures that are described in the Royal Decree 3/2010³⁵, that regulated National Security Schema in electronic administration. This norm described the risks assessment needed for public institution, but after the Data Protection Act will be compulsory in Data Protection analysis.

4.1.2. Intellectual property issues related to works created by AI

³¹ Ibid.

³² Constitutional Court of Spain, cases 110/1984 and 142/1993, 26 November 1984 and 12 March 1993.

³³ Constitutional Court of Spain, cases 11/1998 and 94/1998, 13 January 1998 and 4 May 1998.

³⁴ Spain, Ley Orgánica 3/2018, de protección de datos y garantías digitales (Data protection and Digital warrants), 5 December. 2018, <https://www.boe.es/boe/dias/2018/12/06/pdfs/BOE-A-2018-16673.pdf>

³⁵ Spain, Real Decreto 3/2010, por el que se regula el Esquema Nacional de Seguridad en el ámbito de la Administración Electrónica (National Security Schema in electronic Administration) 8 January 2010. <https://www.boe.es/buscar/pdf/2010/BOE-A-2010-1330-consolidado.pdf>

Based on the law, and our awareness, the Intellectual Property Act (IPA), Real Decreto Legislativo 1/1996³⁶, does not ascribe intellectual property rights for AI generated works or inventions to AI or machines. Although, the creator of the work (article 1 of IPA) could be a machine or an AI, the two rights, personal right and patrimonial right, of intellectual property are only attributable or available to human creators or legal entities, legal figures who are recognised by law to have rights. If we think of AI as an instrument for human creation of intellectual property, such works would fall within the ambit of the general regulation in Intellectual property that is legal person who can execute the right (article 5 of IPA).

In the case of interpreter or a player, a robot or an AI who can play a work, the IPA restrains the concept to a person (article 105).

4.2. Robotics

4.2.1. Creation of a specific legal status for robots

In Spain, the discussion about robotics spins around the economic impact in the society as we have seen above from the study of the White book.

A deep search on the Parliament website to find if there has been any legislative or Non-legislative motion and the search of jurisprudence in the highest courts were both unsuccessful for this topic.

If we look at legal doctrine there is a comment on a collective book about the law of robotics where Barrio Andrés opens the debate about the necessity of a robot law in two aspects: how robots will be regulated in their duties and how should be the legal robots and AI will replace humans on work space.³⁷

About the Constitutional implication, limits and its specific status Barrilao Sánchez talks about the need for constitutional boundaries about the use of robots, especially about the possibility of killing persons. This approach focuses on the constitutional risk of the use of AI and how the use of robots should be limited.³⁸

³⁶ Spain, Real Decreto Legislativo 1/1996, de 12 de abril, por el que se aprueba el texto refundido de la Ley de Propiedad Intelectual, regularizando, aclarando y armonizando las disposiciones legales vigentes sobre la materia (Royal Legislative Decree that regulated Intellectual Property that harmonize, regulate and clarify the different laws in this area), 22 April 1996. <https://www.boe.es/buscar/pdf/1996/BOE-A-1996-8930-consolidado.pdf>

³⁷ Barrio Andrés, Moisés, “Del derecho de internet al derecho de los robots”, in Moises Barrio Andrés (ed.) *Derecho de los Robots*, Wolters Kluwer, Las Rozas, 2018, pp. 61-86.

³⁸ Sánchez Barrilao, José F., “Derecho Constitucional, desarrollo informático e inteligencia artificial: aproximación a la propuesta del Parlamento Europeo a favor de una regulación sobre robótica”, Javier Valls Prieto, *Retos jurídicos por la sociedad digital*, Navarra, Thomson Reuters Aranzadi, 2018, pp. 21-76.

4.2.2. Safety and civil liability issues: who is liable for damage caused by robots?

Currently civil liability as a consequence of robot use is regulated by the general regulation about liability that means there is two ways in the Civil Code to solve the problem: Contract civil liability (article 1101 of the Civil Code)³⁹ and non-contract civil liability (articles 1902 and 1903 of the Civil Code).⁴⁰ With the first one there is an obligation by a contract and if one of the parties act with bad faith or negligence, or act against the obligation, they have to compensate the damages and prejudices caused. With the second liability the person who produced the damages should respond in case of negligence or recklessness. The regulation in this case is really unclear and a case-by-case approach is needed to find a solution⁴¹.

In case there is an end user and they can be considered as consumer it is possible to have recourse under Royal Legislative Decree 1/2007 - its articles 128 to 149 establish that a product is not safe if it does not provide the standard safety that a consumer could expect from a similar product of the same series. To use this norm, first we have to consider a robot as a movable property, but this could be difficult because of the big spectrum of robots that could fall under.⁴²

5. Identify other key specific legal issues related to either AI and robotics that are at the forefront and how they are being addressed

One pertinent issue is criminal liability for robots' acts. At the moment, we can consider the robot as an instrument of the subject who commits a crime. In Spanish criminal law, article 28 of the criminal code would consider the robot as an instrument, as well as an animal could be⁴³.

The question to solve is if autonomous robots would have criminal responsibility, but there are no cases in real life and it still remains a hypothetical issue.

In some of the cases of the analysis done above, and where the impacts have a big risk for FR, it should be protected by criminal law. In Spain privacy attacks by robots or AI could be judged by a criminal court under article 197 of the Criminal Code.⁴⁴ The GDPR, Recital 149 gives Member States the option

³⁹ Gallardo, Marc, "Spain Chapter", Alain Bensoussan and Jérémy Bensoussan (ed) *Comparative handbook: robotics technologies law*, Larcier, Bruxelles, 2016.

⁴⁰ Diaz Alabart, S., *Robots y responsabilidad civil*, Reus, Madrid, 2018.

⁴¹ Gómez-Riesco Tabernero de Paz, Juan, "Los robots y la responsabilidad civil extracontractual", in Moisés Barrio Andrés, (ed.) *Derecho de los Robots*, Wolters Kluwer, Las Rozas, 2018, pp. 107-130.

⁴² Ibid.

⁴³ Domínguez Peco, Elena M., "Robots en el Derecho Penal", in Moisés Barrio Andrés, (ed.) *Derecho de los Robots*, Wolters Kluwer, Las Rozas, 2018, pp. 131-150.

⁴⁴ Valls Prieto, J., *Problemas jurídico penales asociados a las nuevas técnicas de prevención y persecución del crimen mediante inteligencia artificial*, Dykinson, Madrid, 2017.

to lay down the rules on criminal penalties for infringements of the Regulation, including for infringements of national rules, but not all the cases regulated by the GDPR are protected under the Criminal Code.

In the workplace there is a lack of regulation relating to vocational training in formal education, work risk prevention regulations, taxes and pension paid, and robotics and robot codes in the workplaces.⁴⁵

6. Discussion: gaps and challenges

The debate in Spain depends on the interlocutor. For policymakers, Government and Legislative, it centres on the impact of robotics and AI on economics and work market. There is no doubt about the need to advance with the next economic revolution but there are fears and doubts about how it will affect employment.

Jurisprudence has only had the opportunity to build an opinion about the use of algorithms and use of data analysis (automatic decision making) but the Constitutional Court and Supreme Court have not had the opportunity make their opinion heard about these issues.

From the point of view of the doctrine, probably the part from the three identified in this report and have worked more on the topic, it is necessary to make a distinction between those who talk about the AI in the practice of lawyers and Courts, and those who make reference to the problems linked to the use of AI and robotics. In civil law, issues lie in liability and person status of robots and AI. Intellectual property is not an actual problem because classical solutions might solve problems. From Constitutional law perspective, the questions are about fundamental rights impact and how AI and robotics will change the concept of democratic State. Finally, from the criminal law point of view, the questions is how to build and transform the crime to give a right protection to citizens and their fundamental rights and how to use AI to prevent and fight crime, which has a huge impact on privacy rights.

Spain is not at the top of the discussion at the international level, and there are several legal gaps, but in our opinion, in the upcoming years will be important changes in the topics, particularly if these changes come from EU institutions. The legal system in Spain will try to find solutions for the legal challenges of the AI from general solutions. Although there is very few, specific legislation on AI, general solutions can be adapted to this new technology in particular with the interpretation of general rules by the jurisprudence, with special focus on the Constitutional Court. The main gap for this solution is the lack of knowledge of judges about how AI work, but with the proper training this could be addressed. Intellectual property, civil responsibility, criminal responsibility and contract law, with the proper interpretation, could provide solutions for the problems that AI currently presents.

⁴⁵ Serrano Falcón, C., *Robótica avanzada y relaciones laborales: Dificultades, análisis y propuestas*, Digibug, Granada, 2018.

There is a gap related to the GDPR, the lack of privacy impact assessments (PIA) and conduct codes, regulated on article 35 of the GDPR, could be sanctioned by the Spanish Data Protection Act, but there no criminal sanction, as outlined above.

The legal definition of a robot or AI and their legal status could be also important, although in many cases an interpretation of such as an animal or as a slave, as could be in Roman law, could be a first approach with our actual law.

7. Conclusions

The law system in Spain can find solution for many of the problems that robots and AI currently present. Many of them are similar or old problems - already present and addressed in other areas of technology or in real life. Robots and AI make these issues a little bit different but with the right interpretation of the law it is possible to find solution to the challenges that already exists. The constitutional FRs are good enough to provide strong protection against the risks emanating the development of robots and AI at the moment. However, new kinds of digital FRs should probably be introduced, as suggested above along with the proposal of new data protection and digital rights.

The big challenge is how robots will be regulated, independently of their impact on FRs, and if they will have personality in the law system, particular those who can learn by themselves.

The courts have no cases with a direct link to robots or AI and this is one of the problems why there is no big interest from the law practice in this particular area.

As we have verified, 2018 has seen a number of publications related to robots and AI. It is easy to presume that the big explosion of publications in this topic will happen soon. 2018 has also seen Parliamentary activity and while this has always related to economy impact, this first step will most likely be followed by further actions to address the social and human rights impacts and the legal challenge related to them.

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